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of **EXPRESSION**

A Creative Folio

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Norania A. Cabugatan-Mangata, MAEd

Faculty

Mindanao State University-Integrated Laboratory School
Division of Marawi City, Lanao Del Sur, Philippines
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Maybe

I used to count the days in my empty room
Shedding unheard songs of lullabies
Thinking you are here all along,
Losing something precious
So young and vulnerable,
In my young hearts most desires,
Knowing, longing that somehow you exist
In a realm where angel is a bliss

What a wonder would it be
If we see each other full of love and free
I missed you so much that it breaks me
My precious little maybe,
I wonder what would it be
Having you here beside me.

As I remember those happy memory
Praying, that someday you'll gonna see me,
Calling me, "My Mommy"

Grief grew deep as roots in a broken ground of me
It still hurts me today
Somehow guilts eats me
If only I was mindful and extra careful that day
Maybe just maybe
You are growing here with us, with me,
Clinging, laughing and playing with your family.

I wish one day,
I will find my little peace within me
Even if I count those little blessing
That God gave me,
Still grateful for my family but
It would be extra special if you are here with us
My little maybe.